

MODERN METHODS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING
METHODOLOGY.

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Annotation: Learning and teaching foreign languages has become the need of the hour in our country-Uzbekistan as well as in all developed and developing countries. It would not be wrong to say that the conditions created today for young people and all our compatriots for learning foreign languages are proving their positive results. Among the reforms carried out in our country, attention is being paid to foreign languages, especially English. Not only in the case of foreign languages, but also in all areas of the world of science, serious changes and updates are being carried out on all fronts. it is about use.

Keywords: foreign language, innovative technology, methodology, technological tools, modern methods, games.

Thanks to the large-scale reforms implemented in the education system in our country, incomparable opportunities and conditions have been created for the younger generation to acquire modern knowledge and grow up as a perfect person. In today's conditions, it is expedient to train highly qualified personnel on the basis of current systems and modern pedagogical technologies. Advanced and modern pedagogical technologies serve as a guaranteed tool for achieving the goal and show their positive results. In fact, 80% of the successful organization of each lesson depends on the correct development, organization and implementation of the educational process. Today, learning a foreign language requires a spiritual and educational approach to organize each lesson on a unique, unrepeatable level based on the modern educational system and national heritage. To provide young people studying in all educational institutions of our republic: pre-school educational institutions, general secondary schools, vocational colleges, academic lyceums and higher education institutions with modern pedagogical and information technologies, with a new knowledge system continuous organization of armaments is the demand of the times. The role of advanced technologies is very important for the student to express his opinion freely, to explain the topic in a group or team. Therefore, the goals and objectives of teaching a foreign language and its methodology should be in line with and meet the requirements of the interests of our society and the state, as well as the requirements of the young generation.

In today's developing period, changes and significant progress are being made in every field, especially in the field of science. After our country gained independence, attention to science, especially foreign languages, increased. Teaching every subject using modern innovative technologies and methods is one of the most important requirements of today's era. Also, after the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov made a number of decisions on teaching and learning foreign languages, a new environment and era began in our country. According to the decision, modern textbooks, methods and technologies were produced. In today's modern education, the demand for interactive methods, innovative technologies, information technologies to support the educational process is growing day by day. One of the main reasons for this is that in contrast to traditional education until now, when using modern methods, the necessary conditions are being created for the development, formation, and education of the student's personality.

Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired practically in a natural environment, i.e. in the family, among the public or in an organized manner. Knowledge of language phenomena is taught theoretically. Knowledge of languages, especially multilingualism, is of great importance in our time when international relations are on the rise. Pupils and students studying in our country usually study three languages. These languages are referred to by special names. These are: mother tongue, second language, and foreign language. The mother tongue is the first language that plays a special role in the formation of thinking. When talking about the second language, it is considered as the language of relatives and neighbors who are representatives of other nations. A foreign language is the language of a foreign country. Western European languages (English, Spanish, German, French) and Eastern languages (Arabic, Turkish, Persian, Chinese, Indian) are taught in our republic. These languages are included in the curricula of educational institutions. The process of teaching all three languages is different. The mother tongue and the second language are learned in a natural situation, and a foreign language is learned in an artificial environment. Communication in a foreign language mainly takes place in the classroom under the guidance of the teacher. Among the three languages, learning and teaching a foreign language differs sharply in certain aspects. This, in turn, requires the use of appropriate foreign language teaching technology. By carefully mastering the achievements of the methodical science, the foreign language teacher will be able to clearly know the standard of language experience of the student and to improve it further. Effective teaching of foreign languages requires knowledge of its methodology.

The place and role of modern methods and innovative technologies is extremely important. There are several effective ways to teach foreign languages, especially English. In particular, in the course of the lesson, it is possible to show videos in English, dialogues, movies or cartoons, and tape recorders, which are considered a more traditional method, can be used. The use of these technical tools ensures that the process of learning a foreign language is more interesting and effective for students. The importance of modern methods in teaching a foreign language is incomparable. In this place, several methods that are widely used nowadays are being used.

The main concepts of methodology - method, method, principle. Didactics - what do we teach? It is the content of education. Methodology - how do we teach? It means educational methods and methods. Method - the concept of methodology is derived from the Greek-Latin word "methodos-"methodus" and means the means of ways and methods leading to a certain goal. In various literature, the narrow and broad meaning of the term can be found. The term "methodology" in a narrow sense means the concept related to the concrete lesson process of education. It is interpreted as a controlled teaching process that includes instructions related to the planning of lessons and the preparation of teaching materials. The term "method" broadly refers to the selection, classification and distribution of teaching materials. "Didactics" and "methodology" have been used in the narrow sense in the Federal Republic of Germany since the 1960s. Accordingly, what is the content of didactic education taught? How are teaching methods taught? He deals with his issues. Learning foreign languages is not only a means of intellectual education, but also a process of personality formation by getting to know the educational resources and values of a foreign culture and applying them to one's own cultural life. In Europe, the study of foreign languages has long been considered a privilege in higher education, and public schools have been seen as educating the privileged few.

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